

Name: Zarqa Khan

Labour migration as a national development strategy: A Case Study Of India

Introduction:

Migration and globalization are the two most prevalent and interwoven trends that have dominated the global agenda in recent years, with great focus placed on their relationship with development (Mohanty, 2006; Wickramasekara, 2016). Moreover, international migration with high levels of human capital has been recognized as positively leading to growth and long-term stability in countries of origin, transit, and destination (OECD, 2018). According to United Nation (2013) report on global labour migration, there are over 100 million foreign labours residing and working across the world. Moreover, almost half of them are women, who are rapidly moving for employment (United Nation, 2013). In many developing countries out-migrants help to reduce unemployment, poverty and earn international remittances, which contribute to the countries' overall Gross Domestic product (GDP) (Pong-Sul, 2005). Since international migration has served as a safety net, alleviating local labour market pressures, and generating much-needed foreign currency profits, policymakers in developing countries are now formally encouraging labour migration as a national development strategy (Wickramasekara, 2016). However, at the policy level, the rights and protection of migrant workers, as well as the prevention of exploitation, are often overlooked (Wickramasekara, 2016).

The purpose of this essay is to look at labour migration not just as a national development strategy in India, but also from the perspective of social development issues for people who

migrate. Before delving into the argument that migration is seen as a national development strategy in India, it is important to first assess India's entire migration scenario. To begin, the essay will discuss the broader migration-development nexus, as well as the importance of labour migration to the Indian economy. Furthermore, the essay will argue that remittances received via various channels help to drive national economic growth by increasing aggregate spending. The essay will also discuss how the idea of "brain drain" in India has morphed into "brain gain" via returnee migrants and their remittances. Although foreign labour migration has enhanced the Indian economy, the risks associated with it, are substantial, has been extensively examined. Aside from that, the essay will look at present labour migration policies, which need to be re-oriented to offer a legal framework for enhanced labour migrants' protection and welfare. All the arguments in the essay will be supported with evidence and statistics, enabling for a more in-depth understanding of the arguments.

Indian Labour Migration: Historical Overview

Migration in India is not a new phenomenon; it started in the early 18th century, when 30 million Indians crossed borders between 1834 and 1937, with just 24 million returning (Davis, 1951). In addition, 1.5 million Indian labourers were transported to British colonies during the same period under the indentured labour system (Singh, 2021). Since then, migration has grown increasingly prevalent across India, and it has been home to vital resources from all over the world (Khadria et al., 2008; Skeldon, 2010). Khadria et al. (2008) argue that migration of Indian labour during the last two centuries has been initiated and controlled by push forces at home on the one hand and unpredictable demand supply imbalances in recipient countries on the other.

As per UN-DESA (2013) recent report, India is the most populous country of origin for foreign migrants, with a population of over 14 million people. Furthermore, the Indian government predicts that by the turn of the century, the overall number of Indian migrants will rise to 25 million (MOIA, 2012). India's migration policy is split into two geographic areas: the west, that includes the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and European countries, and the east, which includes Singapore, Malaysia, Japan, Korea, and Gulf countries (Khadria et al., 2008). Tejada and Bhattacharya (2014) claim that, India's competent human capital and cheap labour costs have made the nation a major supplier of highly trained, semi-skilled, and unskilled employees for practically every country in the world (Tejada and Bhattacharya, 2014).

According to Khadria (2008), highly skilled Indians often migrate to Western countries since they are the most important and appealing destinations for pursuing their education and career advancement in the fields of engineering, health sector and information technology (IT), engineering, and health care. A recent report by Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) on migrants communities showed that, contemporary Indian migrants are more educated than the local population of several OECD nations (Goldin et al., 2020; OECD, 2017). Furthermore, one in every five highly educated migrants came from India, and the number has more than doubled in the previous decade, so they now comprise a highly educated workforce among The Group of Twenty (G20) nations (OECD, 2017).

While on the other hand, a huge number of semi-skilled or unskilled workers move to the Gulf and South East Asian nations due to the appealing contract employment and higher earnings that push them to leave their home nations (Singh, 2021). According to Kohli (2014), more

than six million Indians live and work in the Gulf countries, which are not only the second biggest overseas Indian population located in a geographical area, but also remit more than one-third of the annual \$69 billion remittances by Indian expats to India. Rajan (2003) claim that, since Indian migrants filled the void left by the chronic scarcity of human resources in the Gulf nations, they are now often preferred over other expatriate populations for work. Furthermore, both the Gulf States and India retain a vibrant and healthy relationship for mutual benefit (Kohli, 2014).

Migration And Development Nexus:

International labour migration, rather than being a problem for development, has become a national development strategy for many developing countries, with the ability to enhance their socioeconomic growth (ILO, 2021). According to United Nation (2010), migration is neither a barrier nor a "magic wand" for its achievement; yet, if managed properly, it may be highly advantageous to both developed and developing nations in terms of achieving international economic development. Labour migration in destination countries may invigorate the workforce, allow labour-intensive businesses such as agriculture, construction, and personal services to continue operating, boost entrepreneurship, support social security systems, and help meet skill demand (ILO, 2021). While the origin nations benefit from remittances and the transfer of capital, technology, and vital skills by returning migrants (World Bank, 2013). Furthermore, remittances pooled via hometown associations and other diaspora organizations finance innumerable relief and development programs and leverage funds from local and national sending communities (Kerwin, 2013). Thus, many experts see international labour migration as a "win-win" solution that should be encouraged since it benefits both the destination and origin countries (Tanner, 2005).

Similarly, migration has become the primary development strategy in India as shown by changes in labour markets, income, assets, and investment patterns (Srivastava and Sasikumar, 2003). Moreover, over 100 million migrant labourers are directly responsible for 10% of India's GDP (Priya Deshingkar, 2020). Kapur (2010) asserts that, the economic effect of foreign migration on India has been principally determined by two primary channels, one financial in which migrant remittances have emerged as a significant element of India's balance of payments. Second is the human capital in the form of skilled and unskilled labour that has released pressure on national labour markets, fulfilled the global labour scarcity and has been playing positive role in building India's reputation in the world (Kapur, 2010). Thus, such instances demonstrate that labour migration seems to be the key survival strategy for Indian policymakers in advancing economic growth, alleviating poverty, and overcoming the country's developmental challenges (De Haan, 2011).

Migration and Remittance Euphoria:

Remittances from migrants are becoming an undeniably powerful source of external development, and they are the most stable source of income that offers social insurance in many nations suffering from economic and political problems (Kapur, 2005). According to Singer (2010), developing nations have long recognized that migrants sending money home to their family are not only a lifesaver for some of the poorest nations, but also account for a considerable portion of the GDP of emerging market nations. In 2004, for example, 42 developing nations had remittance inflows that exceeded 5% of their GDP (Singer, 2010). Furthermore, the World Bank (2008) study showed that, the total documented remittance flows reached \$318 billion in 2007, total verified remittance flows were \$318 billion in 2007,

a staggering figure that surpassed other external financial sources including government aid, credit growth, and capital inflows. Another research by Adams Jr and Page (2005) on international remittances and poverty in 71 developing countries found that remittances considerably lower the degree, depth, and severity of poverty in many developing nations (Adams Jr and Page, 2005).

Likewise, remittances contribute significantly to India's balance of payments and have a strong influence on the country's economy (Singh and Hari, 2011). According to World Bank (2011) report, remittances in India totalled \$55 billion in 2010, accounting for 3% of the country's GDP. Khadria (2008) claim that, India is the world's largest beneficiary of remittances from migrant workers, accounting for more than 10% of the total remittances sent home by 191 million international migrants. Furthermore, increases in remittances have had a significant impact on India's foreign currency reserve, potentially altering many of the country's macroeconomic factors (Azam, 2015). The remittances in India are transferred through two channels: one formal channel that involves financial intermediaries such as banks and postal services, and informal channel in which people choose to send cash through friends or family, which is less expensive (Azam, 2015). As a result, remittance inflows via informal routes are much greater than those via legal ones (Maimbo and Ratha, 2005).

Among all Indian states, Kerala had a lion share of remittances from overseas Indian workers, the majority of which were spent in improving the socioeconomic standing of their families (Khadria, 2008). According to a 1998 household study on migrant remittances, overall remittances to Kerala amounted at Rs. 35,304 million, reflecting an average transfer of Rs. 25,000 per emigrant and a per capita receipt of Rs. 1,105 by the state population (Khadria, 2008). Furthermore, remittances have a considerable economic influence at both the local

and macro levels (Brown et al., 2013). For example, at the micro level, remittances allowed migrant families to pay off debts, acquire land, construct new houses, and invest in the well-being of their children (Weiner, 1982). While, at the macro level, remittances enhanced economic growth, decreased credit limitations, expedited investment, improved human development by funding better education and health, and, most critically, eliminated poverty (Weiner, 1982). Thus, remittances sent by overseas migrants have not only improved the living conditions of individuals in the lowest economic quintiles, but have also contributed to India's overall socioeconomic growth (Parida et al., 2015).

Although remittances contribute significantly to the Indian economy, they are often criticized by many scholars. Weiner (1982) for instance argues that, migrant households utilized remittances primarily for useless expenditure and that they were often squandered. Likewise Wickramasekara (2016) asserts that, when individuals migrate to other nations, a range of distinct statuses emerge with the flow of remittances, resulting in discrimination and inequality. Furthermore, this variety leads to new socioeconomic paradigms and social division, particularly in origin countries (Lu and Treiman, 2007). Remittances to Kerala, for example, resulted in a consumer-driven economy marked by obvious imbalances, lower agricultural productivity, stagnant industrial development, and high unemployment (Kannan, 2005). In addition, since governments consider migration as a safety net for exporting labour, it has resulted in a dependency syndrome, with migration being used as an instrument of dissent rather than development (Wickramasekara, 2016). As a result, migrant remittances are seen as providing some assistance, but they are unable to help nations in overcoming fundamental development challenges such as poverty, inequality, bad governance, poor infrastructure, and a human resource scarcity (Wickramasekara, 2016).

“Brain Drain” Evolving To “Brain Gain”:

For a long time, developing nations have been concerned about the migration of professionals and skilled labour because it is viewed as a "brain drain" and a loss of economic potential (Ramamurthy, 2003). However, Mountford (1997) claims that, in current theoretical debates, the phrase "brain drain" is contrasted with the relatively new phrase "brain gain," which originated in the late 1990s. For instance, "brain gain" refers to the benefits of skilled migration, such as enhanced commerce, remittances, knowledge, capital flows, particularly Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and return migrants' skills, all of which benefit the nations of origin (Schiff, 2005).

According to (Kapur, 2002), the idea of “brain drain” in India has transitioned into “brain gain” with returnee migrants. Several studies have demonstrated that after returning to India, entrepreneurs and professionals play a key role in the country's socioeconomic development (Kapur, 2002). They, for example, transmit advanced technical skills and managerial know-how to others, and develop professional activities, entrepreneurial ventures, and, most significantly, job creation via financial investment (Saxenian, 2005). Similarly (Khadria, 2014) asserts that owing to excessive unemployment, many skilled and unskilled labour migrates to other nations for work; nevertheless, their remittances, investments, and knowledge sharing are significant in mitigating the negative effects of brain drain and bringing fortune to home countries while migrating abroad. For example, in 1991, India was in the midst of financial crises, the resources decreased to a degree that could barely cover basic imports. However, the continuous flow of remittances from skilled and unskilled workers in the Gulf area saved the Indian economy from collapsing (Khadria, 2014). This demonstrates that India's "brain

drain" has not resulted in negative development that exacerbates the country's economic and social problems, but rather has become "brain gain" via dynamic creation within a long process with the prospect of resource benefit for the country (Hunger, 2002).

Exploitation and Abuse of International Labour Migrants:

Although international migration has become an important factor in economic and cultural mutual enrichment for many developing countries, the related risk, especially from a social perspective, is quite significant (Kuzior et al., 2020). According to Khadria (2008), foreign labour migrants are not protected by local labour legislations and hence, endure ongoing vulnerability. Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch (HRW) have published many articles highlighting the extreme vulnerability and exploitation of migrant workers from Asian countries, notably in Arab nations (HRW, 2009). For example, in Lebanon and Jordan, migrant workers live in solitude without complaining about their exploitative working circumstances, and those who raise their voices face the prospect of losing sponsorship, identity cards, and other benefits, which may lead to job loss and deportation (Frantz, 2014). In addition, migrant workers are forbidden from joining trade unions and from participating in any kind of protest for their legal rights (Donini, 2019).

In this sense, migrant labour from India suffers comparable concerns, including as exploitation via the withholding of passports, rejection of promised work and overtime earnings, wage deduction, inadequate medical facilities, denial of legal rights, and sexual assault of women (Khadria, 2008). For example, a recent research by the Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs (MOIA) found that migrant women from India working as housemaids or governesses are subjected to abuses in several Gulf countries, including sexual harassment (MOIA, 2006).

Another study on unskilled and semiskilled labourers in Gulf countries revealed that those working on infrastructure and development projects live in deplorable conditions, with limited restroom and kitchen facilities, and are kept in small restricted quarters in labour camps (Khadria, 2008). Thus, migrant workers, particularly women, in the hunt of opportunities to improve their lives, and escape oppressive social relations, are trapped (Khadria et al., 2008). Consequently, the exploitative working conditions and long periods of separation from families cause emotional depression in many international migrant labours, negatively impacting their overall well-being (Zachariah and Rajan, 2004).

Migration Policy Practice:

Many experts throughout the world have questioned the efficacy of immigration policy, highlighting previous governments' failures to curb immigration and handle migrants' concerns (Bhagwati, 2003). Yong (2016) argues that political philosophers have mainly neglected labour immigration, and approaches to justice in immigration policy do not identify labour as a distinct category. Similarly Bonjour (2011) asserts that, migration policies are often a compromise between opposing interests, with true aims that are frequently varied and, in some instances, essentially contradictory. Businesses, for example, generally lobby for more liberal immigration laws, while trade unions have long seen immigration as a threat to local workers' wages and interests. According to Czaika and De Haas (2013), the most common reason of policy failure is a lack of implementation, since most policies are just on paper and the degree of implementation is impossible to quantify. Thus, Clemens (2018) proposes that policymakers should incorporate immigration policies into national development plans and ensure their implementation, since immigration is inextricably linked to a country's economic development.

In the context of India, despite the existence of the 1922 emigration act, government has had no consistent policy on labour migration or overseas employment, since independence (Khadria, 2008). As a result, in 1983, the current emigration act was replaced by a new one, which was aimed at safeguarding vulnerable groups of unskilled and semiskilled employees, as well as women travelling overseas to work as housemaids and domestic workers (MOIA, 2006). However, Jane (2016) argues that, labour regulations aimed at protecting migrant workers have mostly stayed on paper. For example, the labour contractors often seize migrants' work permits and they did not have pass books, which are required by law and constitute the essential record of their identification and transactions with the contractor and employers (NCRL, 1991).

Therefore, in 2004, a newly formed Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs (MOIA) was established, which took the initiative to revise the Emigration Act of 1983 and implement a variety of policies to safeguard migrant labour rights (Khadria, 2008). For example, it made it essential for all recruitment agencies to register with the Ministry and pipelined all proactive activities for labour migration or abroad employment in accordance with their rights (MOIA, 2006). Despite the efforts by policymakers, the challenges faced by migrant labourers are more complex as shown by the evidence migrant labour are not in a safe and prosperous zone due to the continuous exploitation and abuse they face in migrating countries (Jane, 2016). Thus, International Labour Organization (ILO) suggests that, the current immigration acts and labour policies in India as well as in the migrating countries must be reoriented to create a legal foundation for greater protection and welfare of migrants on the one hand, and active encouragement of international labour migration from India on the other (ILO, 2008).

Conclusion:

To conclude, the above discussion indicates that labour migration is a complex and multifaceted process. Furthermore, labour migration seems to be policymakers' key survival strategy in promoting economic growth, alleviating poverty, and overcoming the country's developmental challenges. The essay argued that, although migrant remittances are important for India's economic progress, they also demonstrate disparities. Furthermore, the concept of "brain drain" is contrasted with the more contemporary phrase "brain gain," which is prevalent in India because of returnee migrants and an overwhelming flow of remittances. Additionally, the essay discussed that, although exporting labour may help the origin countries overcome an economic crisis, the vulnerabilities and exploitation of workers are often disregarded because of poor policy implementation. Thus, as the world's top labour exporter with a remittance-dependent economy, India can achieve more inclusive and equitable development results by including the objective of decent work for everyone and aligning national labour policies with International Labour Organization (ILO) standards.

References

Adams Jr, R.H., Page, J., 2005. Do international migration and remittances reduce poverty in developing countries? *World development* 33, 1645–1669.

Azam, M., 2015. The role of migrant workers remittances in fostering economic growth. *International Journal of Social Economics*.

Bhagwati, J., 2003. Borders beyond control. *Foreign Aff.* 82, 98.

Bonjour, S., 2011. The power and morals of policy makers: Reassessing the control gap debate. *International Migration Review* 45, 89–122.

Brown, R.P., Carmignani, F., Fayad, G., 2013. Migrants' remittances and financial development: Macro-and micro-level evidence of a perverse relationship. *The World Economy* 36, 636–660.

Clemens, M., 2018. Migration Is What You Make It: Seven Policy Decisions that Turned Challenges into Opportunities 32.

Czaika, M., De Haas, H., 2013. The effectiveness of immigration policies. *Population and Development Review* 39, 487–508.

Davis, K., 1951. The population of India and Pakistan.

De Haan, A., 2011. Inclusive growth?: Labour migration and poverty in India. *International Institute of Social Studies The Hague*.

Donini, A., 2019. Social suffering and structural violence: Nepali workers in Qatar, in: *The ILO@ 100*. Brill Nijhoff, pp. 178–199.

Frantz, E., 2014. Breaking the isolation: Access to information and media among migrant domestic workers in Jordan and Lebanon. *Open Society Foundations New York, NY*.

Goldin, I., Koutroumpis, P., Lafond, F., Winkler, J., 2020. Why is productivity slowing down?

HRW, 2009. Slow Movement [WWW Document]. Human Rights Watch. URL <https://www.hrw.org/news/2009/12/16/slow-movement> (accessed 5.27.21).

Hunger, U., 2002. The " Brain Gain " Hypothesis: Third World Elites in Industrialized Countries and Socioeconomic Development in their Home Country.

ILO, 2021. 15. Labour Migration (Decent work for sustainable development (DW4SD) Resource Platform) [WWW Document]. URL

<https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/dw4sd/themes/migration/lang--en/index.htm> (accessed 5.28.21).

ILO, 2008. Managing international labour migration from India: policies and perspectives (Working paper).

Jane, C.A., 2016. Migrant Labour Definition, Challenges, Internal Migrant Labourers, Globalisation, Urbanisation, Migration policies.. 3.

Kannan, K.P., 2005. Kerala's turnaround in growth: Role of social development, remittances and reform. *Economic and Political Weekly* 548–554.

Kapur, D., 2010. Migration and India [WWW Document]. Center for the Advanced Study of India (CASI). URL <https://casi.sas.upenn.edu/iit/dvkapur> (accessed 5.28.21).

Kapur, D., 2005. Remittances: the new development mantra? *Remittances: Development impact and future prospects* 2, 331–360.

Kapur, D., 2002. The causes and consequences of India's IT boom. *India review* 1, 91–110.

Kerwin, D.M., 2013. Does Respect for Migrant Rights Contribute to Economic Development? Migration Policy Institute.

Khadria, B., 2014. The dichotomy of the skilled and unskilled among non-resident Indians and persons of Indian origin: bane or boon for development in India?, in: *Indian Skilled Migration and Development*. Springer, pp. 29–45.

Khadria, B., 2008. India: Skilled migration to developed countries, labour migration to the Gulf. *Migration and development: Perspectives from the South*.

Khadria, B., Kumar, P., Sarkar, S., Sharma, R., 2008. *International migration policy: Issues and perspectives for India*. Citeseer.

Kohli, N., 2014. *Indian Migrants¹ in the Gulf Countries* 34.

Kuzior, A., Liakisheva, A., Denysiuk, I., Oliinyk, H., Honchar, L., 2020. Social Risks of International Labour Migration in the Context of Global Challenges. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 13, 197.

Lu, Y., Treiman, D.J., 2007. The effect of labour migration and remittances on children's education among blacks in South Africa.

Maimbo, S.M., Ratha, D., 2005. Remittances: Development impact and future prospects. The World Bank.

Mohanty, M., 2006. Globalisation, new labour migration and development in Fiji. *Globalisation and governance in the Pacific Islands* 1, 107.

MOIA, 2012. Overseas Indian Affairs [WWW Document]. TGPG. URL <https://tgpg-isb.org/ministry/moia> (accessed 5.27.21).

MOIA, 2006. Annual Report 2005-2006 [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.mea.gov.in/annual-reports.htm?dtl/167/annual+report+20052006> (accessed 5.27.21).

Mountford, A., 1997. Can a brain drain be good for growth in the source economy? *Journal of development economics* 53, 287–303.

NCRL, 1991. National Commission on Rural Labour | WIEGO [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.wiego.org/publications/national-commission-rural-labour> (accessed 5.31.21).

OECD, 2018. How immigrants contribute to developing countries' economies. OECD Publishing.

OECD, 2017. Publications & Documents - OECD [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.oecd.org/g20/topics/employment-and-social-policy/publicationsdocuments/> (accessed 5.27.21).

Parida, J.K., Mohanty, S.K., Raman, K.R., 2015. Remittances, household expenditure and investment in rural India: Evidence from NSS data. *Indian Economic Review* 79–104.

Priya Deshingkar, 2020. LATEST NEWS UPDATES | Why India's migrants deserve a better deal -Priya Deshingkar [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.im4change.org/latest-news-updates/why-india-migrants-deserve-a-better-deal.html> (accessed 5.28.21).

Rajan, S.I., 2003. Dynamics of international migration from India: its economic and social implications, in: *Ad Hoc Expert Group Meeting of Migration and Development*. pp. 27–29.

Ramamurthy, B., 2003. *International labour migrants: Unsung heroes of globalisation*. Sida Stockholm.

Saxenian, A., 2005. From brain drain to brain circulation: Transnational communities and regional upgrading in India and China. *Studies in comparative international development* 40, 35–61.

Schiff, M., 2005. Brain gain: claims about its size and impact on welfare and growth are greatly exaggerated. *The World Bank*.

Singer, D.A., 2010. Migrant remittances and exchange rate regimes in the developing world. *American Political Science Review* 307–323.

Singh, R., 2021. *International migration from India: an historical overview*, in: *Handbook of Culture and Migration*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Singh, S.K., Hari, K.S., 2011. *International migration, remittances and its macroeconomic impact on Indian economy*. IIMA.

Skeldon, R., 2010. Migration and development over twenty years of research: progress and prospects. *migration in a Globalised World* 145.

Srivastava, R., Sasikumar, S.K., 2003. An overview of migration in India, its impacts and key issues, in: Regional Conference on Migration, Development and Pro-Poor Policy Choices in Asia. pp. 22–24.

Tanner, A., 2005. Limitations to Win-win-win in Global Labour Migration. Finnish Yearbook of Population Research 97–116.

Tejada, G., Bhattacharya, U., 2014. Indian skilled migration and development: An introduction, in: Indian Skilled Migration and Development. Springer, pp. 3–26.

UN-DESA, 2013. United Nations Population Division | Department of Economic and Social Affairs [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/data/estimates2/estimatesorigin.asp> (accessed 5.27.21).

United Nation, 2013. Labour Migration And Inclusive Development Setting a Course for Success [WWW Document]. United Nations. URL <https://www.un.org/en/chronicle/article/labour-migration-and-inclusive-development-setting-course-success> (accessed 5.26.21).

United Nation, 2010. Migration Could Greatly Benefit Both Origin, Destination Countries, Agency's Permanent Observer Tells Second Committee | Meetings Coverage and Press Releases [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.un.org/press/en/2010/gaef3291.doc.htm> (accessed 5.28.21).

Weiner, M., 1982. International migration and development: Indians in the Persian Gulf. Population and Development Review 1–36.

Wickramasekara, P., 2016. South Asian Gulf migration to the Gulf: a safety valve or a development strategy? Migration and Development 5, 99–129.

World Bank, 2013. Migration and Development Brief: Migration and Remittances Unit, Development Prospects Group 20. Washington DC: World Bank's Development Prospects Group.

World Bank, 2011. Migration and Remittances Factbook 2011 : Second Edition [WWW Document]. URL <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/2522> (accessed 5.30.21).

World Bank, 2008. Remittance flows to developing countries are estimated to exceed \$300 billion in 2008 [WWW Document]. URL <https://blogs.worldbank.org/peoplemove/remittance-flows-to-developing-countries> (accessed 5.29.21).

Yong, C., 2016. Justice in Labour Immigration Policy: Social Theory and Practice 42, 817–844. <https://doi.org/10.5840/soctheorpract201642429>

Zachariah, K.C., Rajan, S.I., 2004. Gulf revisited economic consequences of emigration from Kerala: emigration and unemployment.